

THE CONCEPT OF THE "ARIF" IN IRFAN

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Резюме. В данной статье исследуется этимология термина «ариф-гностик», отличительные и сходственные черты суфиев и гностиков, а также суфизма и гностицизма. Выявляются общие черты их мировоззрения, психологических состояний и жизни деятельности. Путем сравнительного метода исследуется отличие между гностиками (ариф) и аскетами (захид, абид). Описываются отличительные черты деятельности гностиков и ученых. Исследуется пути достижения Истины (Хакк) гностиками.

Ключевые слова: Суфий, Ариф, Абид, Захид, Ирфан, Суфизм

Summary. Ethnology of the term “arif-gnostic” is distinctive and resembles characteristics of sufies and gnostiks, also sufizm and gnostisizm are researched in this article. It has exposed common characteristics of their outlook, psychological positions and life activities. Differences between Gnostics and ascetics are researched by means of comporative methods. Distinctive characteristics of Gnostics and scientists are described in this summary. The ways of achievinq truth-God are researched by Gnostics .

Keywords: mistic, gnostic, ascetic, gnostisizm, mistisizm

Introduction:

Before speaking about irfan, one must first sense, feel, and internalize it. In our view, a believer who lacks the love of God in their heart cannot truly speak about irfan; and if they do, it will be no more than a misrepresentation. The word "arif" is of Arabic origin and is derived from the root “arf,” meaning “one who knows, perceives, is aware, wise, one who recognizes spiritual states, and understands subtle truths.” Irfan, likewise, comes from the same root and signifies “knowledge of God” or “mysticism.”

As a term, irfan is used in two senses: the first is theoretical irfan, which is based on the Qur’an and Hadith, and from which a rich tradition of religious-philosophical treatises and mystical poetry has developed. The second is practical irfan, which draws upon the lifestyle and spiritual practices of the Prophet (PBUH) and his companions. In the practical dimension of irfan, we find parallels with the practices of arifs (gnostics) and Sufis.

Before delving into the main topic, we should briefly explain the term “mysticism”: in the context of irfan and Sufism, mysticism is far removed from its literal meaning of “secret” or “enigma.” Rather, it refers to the inner, spiritual experience of perceiving and feeling God through the heart. Since this state is not attainable by every servant, throughout history many mystics have been persecuted and accused of heresy. Currently, both in the East and the West, the lifestyles and works of Islamic mystics continue to generate significant interest.

Within irfan, one can occasionally encounter ideas resembling those of various philosophical and religious traditions—such as the Brahmins, representatives of Buddhism, Stoics, Nestorians, ascetics, Neoplatonists, and even Zoroastrians. This resemblance is quite natural, as all these traditions were born out of a common quest for truth, and their followers possessed a foundation of religious knowledge. Over time, due to increasing human interaction and cultural integration, such knowledge spread both orally and through manuscripts.

Even in our Holy Book—the Qur’an—there are references to pre-Islamic religions, where both their positive and negative attributes are discussed. Given the historical and social context in which irfan developed, some degree of influence from other religious and philosophical systems was

inevitable. However, it must be emphasized that irfan is fundamentally rooted in the divinity of God and the concept of prophethood—its core being the recognition of the One Creator.

As stated in the Surah Al-Baqarah:

"Indeed, we belong to Allah, and indeed to Him we will return." (2:156)

The arifs (gnostics) firmly believe that the human soul, as a fragment of the Divine, will eventually return to its Source. Islam, above all else, introduces God to humanity as He defines Himself, rejecting the notions of God's personification or materialization found in pre-Islamic traditions such as Christianity or Buddhism. Instead, Islam is grounded in tawhid—the belief in the absolute oneness of God.

The Sufi and the Arif:

It is impossible to conceive of irfan without tasawwuf, and likewise, tasawwuf without irfan. Tasawwuf is the path that leads to irfan; metaphorically speaking, irfan stands at the peak of the spiritual journey. Simply put, irfan is the highest form of tasawwuf, and this state is attainable only by the arifs (gnostics). It must be noted that while every arif is a Sufi, not every Sufi reaches the level of an arif. Not all who set out on this difficult and trial-filled path of tasawwuf succeed in attaining the station of arifhood. For this reason, the two concepts should not be equated.

If a Sufi lacks firm resolve and conviction, they may falter along the way, abandon the path, or—even worse—pretend steadfastness and fall into false Sufism to preserve their image. In contrast, an arif is the one who, having benefited from tasawwuf, has stepped into the realm of irfan. At the stage of arifhood, the path only moves forward—there is no descent. In other words, just as a cooked dish cannot be reverted to its raw state, an arif cannot be taken backward in spiritual terms.

As Mawlana Rumi famously expressed:

"Kham budam, pokhte shodam, sukhtham"

("I was raw, I became cooked, I was burned").

This phrase symbolizes the transformative journey of the soul through stages of spiritual refinement, culminating in divine union and annihilation of the self (fana).

With a somewhat bold comparison, one might say that if a true Sufi is a diamond, then the Arif is a gem that has been meticulously cut, polished, and refined from that diamond—reflecting the brilliance of the sun, unmatched in hardness, and capable of polishing others by its own radiance.

The roots of Irfan, which encompasses both practical and theoretical dimensions, must be sought in the depths of the mysterious soul and being of the human, considered the noblest of all creation. In essence, Irfan represents the spiritually attained positive state of a human being. It is a refined psychological condition, whereby a person who has ascended to such a spiritual level undergoes a complete transformation in worldview.

Irfan is not a transient quality; on the contrary, it brings about a revolutionary shift in the consciousness of the Sufi-Arif who enters into this state. The individual is cleansed of aggression, envy, and other ego-driven tendencies. The person attains a profound tranquility and, in this state, becomes indifferent to all material possessions.

In contemporary terms, this positive psychological condition—or spiritual state—cannot occur independently of what we call the "soul" or the "heart." Rather, it is deeply intertwined with these inner dimensions of human existence. A person who is free from anger, rage, and aggression naturally becomes a possessor of great patience and composure, which is clearly reflected in their subsequent actions and behavior. Irfan is such a powerful domain that it elevates a human—originally bound to the material world through physical existence—to the sublime realm of the unseen (ghayb), to the Absolute Being, that is, to God.

An individual who has attained irfan transforms into an elevated human being through their positive mindset and righteous conduct. Psychologically distanced from worldly and carnal desires, freed from aggression, and viewing all beings as equal creations of God rather than through a hierarchical or discriminatory lens, the arif finds contentment in the divine blessings granted to him. He constantly lives with a deep sense of need for and gratitude to God. The arif who has reached divine love experiences the state of baqa (subsistence in God) after the state of fana (annihilation of

the self). In finding eternity in the countenance of God, the arif leads his disciples through the spiritual journey of suluk, guiding them on the path of inner purification. For the arif—whose heart's eye, the eye of inner insight (basirat), has witnessed the majesty of the Divine—worldly fear loses all value. The arif fears only one thing: incurring the wrath of God. To avoid deviating from this path, he constantly protects himself from spiritual defilement through the remembrance (dhikr) of God. To worship the Truth (Haqq) in a state free from egotism and the prison of materialism, to immerse one's heart in Divine light, and to live with unwavering faith in God—this is the aspiration of those who walk the path of irfan. Throughout history, the people of irfan have held the conviction that in order to reach the station of arifhood and witness the Divine with the eye of the heart, one must undergo a series of spiritual stages. Only through this process, and by virtue of one's inner potential, can one attain true understanding of the Divine and reality (Haqq). For the arif, who has personally witnessed the existence and majesty of God, no further proof is necessary. The arif loves God through divine love (ishq) without the need for rational evidence. In this respect, arifs differ from philosophers who require logical proof of God's existence. An arif is not an ascetic who renounces everything. To possess material wealth does not necessarily mean to be attached to it. There are those who, despite owning great riches, are not attached to them and spend their wealth along the path prescribed by God.

Arifs constantly observe the hadith attributed to Imam Ali (a): "The greatest form of faith is hidden faith." In other words, people may not even realize that the arif leads a life of spiritual seclusion. This hadith states that God has hidden His friends (awliya, the saints) among His servants, and thus, one should never harm another person—he may in fact be one of those hidden friends of God.

Some sources state: "The similarity between Sufism (tasawwuf) and 'irfan lies in their shared objective, while the difference between them is found in the methods and paths used to reach that objective. The 'arif follows the methods prescribed by the Prophet (PBUH) and the Ahl al-Bayt, whereas the Sufi is free to choose his path and follows the voice of his own heart." (5)

Indeed, both Sufism and 'irfan share the same ultimate goal: to attain the Truth (al-Haqq). However, it should not be forgotten that a true Sufi, after traversing the stages of sulūk within Sufism, eventually arrives at the station of 'irfān. In 'irfān, the stages of sulūk are more strictly directed toward maintaining constant connection with the Divine and avoiding deviation from the path.

Therefore, the Sufi is not entirely free in his choices, as he does not independently pass through the spiritual stages. Rather, he is guided by a perfected spiritual master (murshid, pir, or shaykh) who leads him along the way. The Sufi advances through each stage only under the strict supervision and guidance of this spiritual authority to ensure his progress is correct and complete.

Ascetic, Devotee, and Gnostic:

When analyzing the activities of Sufis and gnostics ('urafā'), it is appropriate to refer to the work *Al-Isharat* by Abu Ali Sina (Avicenna, 980–1037). He writes about the zāhid (ascetic), 'ābid (devotee), and 'ārif (gnostic):

"He who renounces worldly possessions and pleasures is called a zāhid (ascetic). One who gives great attention to prolonged supererogatory worship, such as fasting and staying awake all night in prayer and supplication, is an 'ābid (devotee). The one who devotes his thoughts and contemplations solely to the power and sanctity of the Truth (al-Haqq), and whose spirit becomes the locus of divine manifestations, is an 'ārif (gnostic). At times, these three categories are confused, and people try to conflate asceticism with gnosis." (*Al-Isharat*, vol. 1, p. 430)

Avicenna further states:

"The ascetic, when compared to the gnostic, is like a merchant or a tradesman, who, as it were, trades the privileges of this world for the rewards of the hereafter. For the 'ārif, purification and the avoidance of base desires are everything, and he holds nothing above God.

Worship for one who is not a gnostic is a kind of transaction — performing deeds in this world in exchange for rewards in the next. But for the 'ārif, worship is a sacrifice made in the path of divine

mercy and majesty. Once the power of imagination and perception becomes habitual in the ‘arif, he turns away from the threshold of his own ego toward the Divine Presence.” (Al-Isharat, vol. 1, p. 431)

From the above, it becomes clear that for the ‘arif (gnostic), worship is merely a means to attain union with the Divine. The love for God is so profound in the ‘arif that living without worship is inconceivable; he constantly dwells in the atmosphere of divine love.

Abu Ali Sina (Avicenna) further notes:

“For the ‘arif, servitude to the Divine Presence is not based on fear or hope — rather, servitude itself is an honor. If worship is done out of fear, greed, or hope for something, then the true purpose of such worship becomes the fulfillment of a desire or the removal of a fear. In such worship, the ultimate goal is not God, but the attainment of that desire, and God is seen only as a means. (Al-Isharat, vol. 1, p. 432)

Turning away from worldly pleasures and engaging in constant worship — as seen with ascetics and devotees — is not free from fear and greed. In contrast, for the ‘arif, the ultimate purpose in prayer and devotion is God Himself, for His pleasure is above all blessings and miracles.

The ‘arifin (gnostics) base this belief on the Qur’an, specifically in the chapter at-Tawbah, where it is stated:

“Allah has promised the believing men and women gardens beneath which rivers flow, wherein they will dwell forever, and pleasant dwellings in Gardens of Eden. But the greatest of all is Allah’s pleasure—that is the ultimate triumph.” (9:72)

This verse highlights that divine pleasure surpasses all material or spiritual rewards, and it is this pleasure that the ‘arif truly seeks.

As Mawlānā (Rūmī) eloquently states:

قبله عارف بود نور وصال	قبله عقل مفلس شد خیال
قبله زاهد بود یزدان بر	قبله طامه بود همیان زر
قبله معنی و ران صبر و درنگ	قبله صورت پرستان نقش سنگ
قبله باطن نشینان ذوالمنن	قبله ظاهر پرستان روی زن

(9, p. 971)

The qibla (spiritual direction) of the ‘arifs’ (gnostics) is the light of union with the Truth (Haqq). The light of a philosophizing intellect is but illusion. The qibla of the ascetic (zahid) is the God who bestows blessings; the greedy seek the qibla of a purse full of gold. Those seeking meaning find their qibla in patience and tranquility, while image-worshippers focus on the patterns carved in stone. The qibla of those who have reached the spiritual realm is the noble and gracious God, whereas the outwardly focused (zahirpærast) fixate on the form of a woman.

The views of Mawlānā and Ibn Sina on the worship of the arifs perfectly coincide: the arif’s worship aims at attaining union with the Truth, which differs fundamentally from the mentalities of the ascetic, the devotee, and the philosopher.

Scholar and Arif:

The word arif translates from Arabic as “one who knows.” In the Qur’an, Allah’s attribute of being ‘alim—All-Knowing—is emphasized, describing Him as the one who knows everything completely and perfectly, without any deficiency or partner.

The Qur’an frequently uses the term ‘alim for God, which is among His beautiful names. ‘Alim refers to the One who knows the unseen, hidden realities unknown to creation. Since Allah is the Creator of space and time, His knowledge is not limited by them. Allah’s knowledge is incomparable to that of His servants; it is eternal, boundless, and without limits—an original and everlasting knowledge.

Although the words arif and alim both generally mean “one who knows,” they are used with different connotations in Sufi literature. An alim is typically someone knowledgeable, engaged in the study of sciences, and devoted to acquiring intellectual knowledge. In contrast, an arif is a perfect person or saint (wali)—one whose understanding, intuition, and perception are highly developed—who knows the attributes, names, and actions of God through discovery and observation, and who is deeply acquainted with divine wisdom and secrets. The knowledge acquired by an alim is ‘ilm

(scientific or intellectual knowledge), while that acquired by an arif is ma'rifah (spiritual gnosis). (2, p. 72)

If the alim seeks explanation, evidence, and proof in everything, the arif relies on the heart and ethical principles in their spiritual practice. While the alim attains knowledge to move away from ignorance, the arif ascends to the pinnacle of spiritual perfection through inner purification. The lifestyle of an alim may not always be exemplary, but an arif cannot embark on the path of spiritual journeying (suluk) without complete purification from all carnal and worldly desires.

For the alim, intellect, reasoning, and speech are the primary tools; for the arif, divine love for God is paramount and surpasses intellect. The arif in a state of mystical observation (mushahada) cannot express with words what the heart's eye perceives and feels. According to the arifs, in such a state, language, intellect, and reason all fail. There must be no veil between the lover who has reached the Truth and the Beloved.

For the alim (scholar), the world is a mystery full of enigmas and secrets to be investigated; for the arif (gnostic), the world is the manifestation and reflection of God's self-disclosure.

The perspectives of philosophers and arifs on life differ significantly. Philosophers seek to comprehend the world and obtain precise knowledge about it. According to philosophers, the highest degree of human perfection is to understand the world exactly as it is through intellectual reasoning.

In contrast, the arif does not primarily rely on intellectual reasoning. The arif aspires to reach and unite with God, who is the ultimate reality and meaning of existence.

From the arif's viewpoint, reaching human perfection is not achieved merely by forming intellectual concepts of existence. True perfection involves overcoming the distance and obstacles between the human and God, thereby attaining eternity in the presence of God.

While the philosopher's methods and means are thought, logic, and rational argumentation, the arif relies on the heart, inner struggle, action, purity, and spiritual cleanliness.

Arifs distinguish themselves from other scholarly and cultural groups within Islamic civilization, such as mufassirs (Quranic exegetes), mutakallims (theologians), muhaddiths (hadith scholars), fuqaha (jurists), philosophers, and literati. This distinction lies in the fact that arifs, besides existing as a cultural stratum and producing a body of knowledge called irfan (gnosis), nurturing great scholars within their ranks, and creating valuable works, have also formed a unique social class within the Islamic world. In contrast, fuqaha, philosophers, and other scholars have remained solely as cultural groups and have not developed into organized social classes within society.

In reality, irfan has both cultural and socio-political roots. For this reason, those engaged in irfan are culturally referred to as "arif," while socially and communally they are known as "mutasawwifs" (Sufis). It is important to note, however, that arifs and sufis did not arise from religious fragmentation within Islam; rather, despite spreading across all Islamic sects, they maintained a strong and well-organized social group identity. In this respect, they can be compared to Freemasons. Their distinct worldview, specific behavioral codes, and, unlike Freemasons, their unique dress code (wearing the khirqa), residence in khanqahs (Sufi lodges), and other characteristics set them apart as a special religious-social group.

Morality and Irfan. Religion is generally divided into three parts: 1. Creed (Aqidah), 2. Morality (Akhlaq), and 3. Practice (Amal).

Broadly speaking, the science of morality deals with two main issues: 1. Destructive traits—vices and negative characteristics, and 2. Salvific traits—virtues and positive characteristics.

According to the science of morality, a person should possess praiseworthy qualities and behavior in life, adorn themselves with noble human traits, understand their duties and responsibilities, be benevolent, love people, and strive to be kind, loyal, good-natured, cheerful, and just. One must defend truth, avoid overstepping the limits of their rights, respect the lives, property, and honor of others, spare no effort in teaching knowledge and manners, and establish justice in all areas of life. In short, one should rid themselves of destructive traits and cultivate salvific ones.

In this regard, there is a similarity between morality and irfan, though there are also differences.

Murtaza Mutahhari, in his book *Introduction to Islamic Sciences*, divides this difference into three parts: “First, irfan concerns a person’s relationship with themselves, the world, and God, focusing primarily on the connection between the servant and God. However, not all ethical systems consider examining a person’s relationship with God necessary; only religious-ethical systems emphasize and pay attention to this matter.”

Second, unlike the established and fixed science of ethics, irfani (mystical) spiritual journey is evolutionary and dynamic. It describes the purpose, destination, and stages that a seeker (salik) passes through sequentially, from the starting point to the final goal.

Third, the moral elements of the soul are limited in meaning and concept and are generally easy to recognize. In contrast, the irfani elements of the soul are much broader and more encompassing. The mystical journey (seyrū-sūluk) involves various states and emotions that only the seeker on the path of Truth can experience through passing certain stages, engaging in spiritual practices, and undergoing inner struggles. Others remain unaware of these conditions.

It should be noted that arifs (mystics) are ranked according to the extent of their spiritual knowledge (marifat).

Thus, an arif is one who, by following the path of the Prophets and the Ahl al-Bayt, succeeds in recognizing the true Reality and distinguishes themselves in their lifestyle and actions. The arif grounds their beliefs on the verses of the Holy Quran, relying on Tawhid (the Oneness of God). Guided by Tawhid and the truths of the hereafter, they refine their principles of thought, morality, action, and spiritual states.

Shams al-Din Muhammad Lahiji (1506–1507 AH), in his commentary on Sheikh Mahmud Shabustari’s (1288–1321) *Gulshan-i Raz*, answers the question “Who is an arif?” as follows: “An arif is one who has been annihilated and effaced in their own existence; the true arif is nothing other than the perfect human being.”

When Husayn ibn Ali Yazdan Yardan asked when the arif (mystic) perceives Haqq (the Truth), he replied: “As soon as the Witness (Mashuq—Beloved) appears, the observer (the lover) is annihilated, and his other faculties vanish; the sincerity and happiness of the arif are also nullified.” In other words, these are the characteristics of the arif when he beholds Haqq. Everyone sees Haqq in the Witness, while in the observer they see the people. Once Haqq becomes manifest to the arif, the arif becomes annihilated in himself. This means that his desires disappear—there remains no sense of benefit derived from longing. For example, the eye’s purpose is to see, seeing’s purpose is to discern, and discerning’s purpose is to enjoy. But when the arif’s mind is absorbed in Haqq during observation, his eyes derive no pleasure from seeing and do not discern. It is as if nothing remains visible to his eyes. His other senses experience a similar condition. The nullification of his sincerity is not hypocrisy; rather, in this state, he is more sincere than the sincere, though he himself does not perceive this sincerity. (7, pp. 254–257)

Abu Turab Nakhshabi (859 AH) states: “An arif is one who is never saddened nor distressed by anything.” (8, p. 549)

From the above, it can be concluded that the stages of spiritual progression (seyru-suluk) in irfan lead the individual solely to the pinnacle of perfection. The state of fana (annihilation) does not imply the destruction of the arif’s spirituality, but rather the annihilation of the ego and sensual desires, which renders worldly attachments utterly insignificant and effectively destroyed. Ibn Sina’s analogy related to the eye demonstrates that during observation, the arif becomes completely indifferent to material existence perceivable by the physical eye. The main issue is the annihilation of the “self” or “ego.” In the state of fana, only the inner eye (the “third eye”)—the eye of the heart—remains active, which functions solely by the capacity granted by the human soul. It is only after this state of fana that many secrets of Haqq can be revealed to the arif.

Ibn Arabi (1165–1240) writes in his work *Fusus al-Hikam*: “The arifs perceive their knowledge as recognizing Haqq and His names, attributes, and manifestations.” Ibn Arabi bases the knowledge of those called “people of Haqq” and “people of irfan” on seven key issues, emphasizing that a person

deeply acquainted with these will find the recognition of Haqq neither difficult nor any of Haqq's commands hidden from them. He explains the seven issues as follows:

1. The recognition of Haqq,
2. The recognition of His manifestations,
3. The recognition of the divine commands expressed through the Sharia,
4. The recognition of perfection and its existence and deficiencies,
5. The recognition of one's own realities,
6. The knowledge of imagination and its unification and separation,
7. The knowledge of ailments and their remedies.

(Ibn Arabi clarifies that these ailments are not physical illnesses but relate specifically to the spiritual maladies concerning speech (connected to thought), actions, and states of being, which are known only to arifs and sheikhs.) (10, p. 571)

Naturally, the term "ailments" as used by Ibn Arabi can be understood as imperfections or deficiencies. According to the scholar, the existence of imperfection arises from perfection itself, for without imperfection, perfection cannot be realized; every human ascends from deficiency to perfection.

According to Ibn Arabi's creed, the source of the arif's knowledge (ma'rifah)—meaning recognition, awareness, and understanding—is the heart. Regarding the heart, Ibn Arabi's foremost commentator, Abdulrazzaq Kashani (d. 1329 AH), writes in *Kitab al-Istilahat al-Sufiyya*: "The heart is an essence endowed with an immaterial light that lies between the soul (ruh) and the self (nafs). Scholars call this the 'speaking self' (nafs al-natiqa). The human being, inwardly complex with the soul and outwardly an animalistic self, expresses himself through this." (10, p. 571)

In conclusion:

Thus, the arif is one who sees, hears, and recognizes nothing except God; speaks of nothing but the Truth (Al-Haqq); desires nothing but God; inclines toward nothing else; and progresses toward no other destination. The path of their heart leads only to God.

The arif is one who is aware of the divine laws and implements them. In other words, the arif is righteous before God and kind toward fellow human beings. The fundamental principle of the arifs is "not to be of this world, yet to live in this world," a concept that may seem very difficult or even incomprehensible from the perspective of an ordinary person.

In essence, arifs are those deeply enamored with Haqq, whose spiritual worship is incomprehensible to ordinary people. The arif's constant reliance is solely on God. It must be noted that arifs are great scholars who strictly observe the laws set by God, avoid all prohibitions decreed to humanity, and unquestionably attain divine knowledge.

In every respect, the arif is a person whose entire being, beyond theoretical and practical experience, is wholly directed toward Haqq. Like the Prophets, the arif abstains from the forbidden, successfully performs obligatory and supererogatory worship, and progresses through the stages of spiritual journey (seyrū-süluk). Ultimately, through observation, the arif reaches the state of fana-fillah (annihilation in God) and then baqa-billah (subsistence through God).

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